

Cultural analytics to discover regularities in cultural movements: A book review

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Figure 1: A kingfisher doing cultural analytics. Image created by DALLE via ChatGPT.

Although they are both kingfishers, part of the same family, yet her beak is petite and elegant. Her eyes are sharp but sparkled with a hint of charm. Her delicate figure embodies the phrase “a swan’s grace,” yet she possesses incredible strength, easily lifting a three-ounce fish up to her branch. But most importantly, her ethereal attire earns her the title of “Dreamy Wings.” Her entire being is like an ethereal painting, a playful creation of nature using colors, lines, dots, strokes, and patches. One can only exclaim, “Absolutely enchanting. Is this real or an illusion?”

- In *The Philosophy of Awakening, Wild Wise Weird: The Kingfisher Story Collection*, Vuong (2025)-

In *Cultural Analytics*, Lev Manovich (2020) outlines the recent developments and the historical roots of a new, exciting research field called cultural analytics. Cultural analytics emerges as a discipline that utilizes methods from computer science, data visualization, and media arts for the exploration and analysis of cultural objects and their user interactions. In other words, cultural analytics studies cultures *at scale* via digital and computational methods.

How humanities benefit from cultural analytics

Manovich argues the humanities can have twofold benefits from cultural analytics. First, the humanities, traditionally very qualitative, start seeing how the principles of the hard sciences can be applied to their research subjects with the rise of big data and accessible computational tools. Second, more importantly, as it inherits from methods and perspectives from a number of fields such as science and technology studies (STS), software studies, digital humanities, cultural analytics research not only apply these computational tools but also remain critical at questioning assumptions and biases laden in cultures and societies, including critically examining the “quantitative turn” of art and media studies as well. As the author stated: “Cultural analytics for me is the instrument to question all categorical boundaries.” (p.13). Indeed, as an emerging field, cultural analytics also probes theoretical and practical questions about the limitations of studying culture with computational methods and large-scale analysis. In 12 chapters, Manovich leads us through a series of key concepts, methods, seminal studies, theoretical and practical issues that form the foundation for cultural analytics. For the sake of pedagogical utility, the twelve chapters are logically divided into three parts: part I familiarizes readers with examples of the field; part II serves as a methodological crash course of conceptual operations, choices, and constraints in generating datasets from cultural artifacts; and part III provides nuanced discussions on data visualization.

Studying culture at scale

Critically, the book poses many deep questions for and guides readers to see *culture at scale*. Since our lives now are increasingly digitized, tracked, and mediatized (Ho & Vuong, 2024), quantitative large-scale studies of cultural behaviors, including discussing, reading, listening, viewing, etc., have become possible. As clearly articulated in the twelve research challenges, carefully deployed computational methods on well-defined research questions in cultural and media studies can yield not only interesting results but also potentially lead to new discoveries of *regularities* in cultural movements. In other words, cultural analytics allow researchers to investigate not only contemporary phenomenon but also deep into the past and make prediction for the future. The author goes on to state that the discoveries and tracking of cultural DNAs and their manifested phenotypes (i.e., cultural behaviors) are possible.

Here, by frequently referring to the classic works in the humanities such as the famous critique of the cultural industry by Adorno and Horkheimer, which states “Culture today is infecting everything with sameness,” Manovich asks how the computational media analytics of today affect the products created by the culture industry and the choices of the consumers. Connecting the past and contemporary cultural studies, Manovich creates an infectious exciting feeling about what discoveries might be in front of us.

Computational studies on past cultural artifacts

Computational studies on past cultural artifacts can indeed yield astonishing new ideas and insights and help us rethink scientific concepts as well. For example, codifying the appearances of traditional cultural values and symbols (e.g., of Buddhism, Confucianism, Taoism) in folktales (Vuong et al., 2018) and satirical cartoons (Ho et al., 2021) have enabled researchers to reach deeper appreciation of concepts that represent cultural mixing mechanisms such as cultural additivity, cultural hybridity, cultural syncretism, etc.. Or computationally studying the digitized editorials of newspapers from 1827 to 1865 reveals the importance of the invisible labor of women as well as the Black press in the Abolitionist movement (Soni, Klein, & Eisenstein, 2021). Another example is Candia et al. (2019) show the average attention received by cultural products decays following a universal biexponential function, and biographies stay in our collective memory the longest (20-30 years), while music the shortest (about 6 years). Such an attempt to understand the law of collective memory decay can only be possible by analyzing the patterns of millions of citations received by academic articles and online attentions (votes, play counts, mentions, etc.) received by hundreds of thousands of cultural products (movies, music records, biographies).

The readers also benefit greatly from Manovich 's utmost care and rigor in differentiating among different commonly used terminologies such as algorithms, analytics, software. For example, Manovich refrains from using the word algorithms in association with the studies of culture and explains the preferred terms are software and analytics for they do not presume the use traditional algorithms, which executes a finite sequence of steps, nor do they assume interpretability. Or in discussing how to represent cultural phenomenon as data, Manovich prefers the term feature over variable, as the former does not assume a particular statistical paradigm.

Future researchers, especially those in STS, can also derive great insights from the theoretical and practical gaps in cultural analytics being explained in the book. An example is the lack of organized efforts to build any systematic theory of cultural sampling (i.e., how to define representative cultural samples, what methods to construct such a sample, what statistical estimates of what can be learned with it and with what certainty, etc.). Indeed, STS-minded readers can, at the same time, appreciate the new affordances of computational techniques for cultural studies and remain critical and ask big-picture questions critically on ontological and epistemological issues related to the new scientific and technological progress (Sismondo, 2011).

The book does well in providing a balance between the philosophical discussions regarding cultural research in the age of data abundance and the technical, practical details that involved in data treatment and methods selection (Patton, 2004). For example, Manovich points out one can see how the rise of advanced computational methods and big data allows for a hermeneutical cycle between the positivist and the constructivist approach. For example, to analyze museum paintings, one can create a dataset based on existing, socially acknowledged labels (where meanings have already been constructed) or one can use feature extraction algorithms to extract low-level features (e.g., edges, shapes, colors, objects, etc.) of the paintings then feed them into cluster-discovering algorithms to discover whether computer-generated features and clusters produce categories that match the existing ones or not.

Throughout the book, Lev Manovich illustrates and emphasizes the importance, even necessity of big data for the emerging ‘hard’ science of cultural studies. However, there is an equal emphasis on the fact that cultural data must not only be big but also rigorous and clever. Manovich continuously admonishes future researchers to think hard about the challenges of how cultural phenomenon can be represented as data to avoid the reductivism trap, as he quotes Gitelman and Jackson: “our zeal for more and more data can become a faith in their neutrality and autonomy, their objectivity. . .” Clearly, big, clever, and rigorous data must be the foundation for the advance of science in the 21st century.

Book information

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